

NEW TEST METHODS FOR CHARACTERISING SKIN-CORE DEBONDING IN COMPOSITE SANDWICH STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY: The interfacial fracture properties of a series of fibre reinforced sandwich materials have been investigated using a number of different test techniques. The results have shown that relatively simple test geometries such as the single cantilever sandwich (SCS) specimen and the three point bend sandwich (TPBS) specimen are well suited to characterising the interfacial fracture properties of these lightweight materials. Both of these geometries also offer the advantage that they can be used to determine the interfacial fracture energy of sandwich materials at impact rates of strain.

KEYWORDS: sandwich materials, delamination, interfacial fracture, debonding.

INTRODUCTION

The use of high performance, light-weight sandwich materials has increased significantly in recent years. Typically, carbon and glass fibre reinforced plastics are bonded to low density cores to produce strong, stiff lightweight structures. The strength of the interface between the composite facing and the low density core is likely to be critical and needs to be optimised before these materials will achieve their full potential. To date, much of the work relating to skin-core adhesion in sandwich structures has involved the use of the climbing drum test where the skin is wrapped around a large radius cylinder mounted on one side of the specimen. The test suffers several limitations, however. One of these relates to the fact that the skins must be relatively thin and flexible. It is also difficult to undertake tests at high rates of loading, a loading condition that might result in a significant reduction in the fracture properties of these materials. Recently, Prasad and Carlsson [1,2] used a modified double cantilever beam specimen to evaluate debonding and crack kinking in foam core sandwich beams. In an earlier study, Carlsson et al [3] developed a cracked sandwich beam specimen to investigate shear failure in a GFRP-balsa sandwich structure. Their results indicated that the interfacial fracture toughness values of such materials can be much greater than those associated with traditional thermoset-based composite materials.

The authors recently developed a number of new tests to characterise skin-core adhesion in sandwich structures. These tests involve propagating a crack along the skin-core interface and determining an interfacial fracture energy. The objective of this work was to assess the interfacial fracture properties of sandwich materials using these tests and two traditional tests

used widely in industry. The advantages and limitations of the test procedures will be highlighted and discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Materials

Four glass/polyester balsa systems (referred to as materials A to D) manufactured via a hand lay-up process were considered in this study. The skins in all materials were based on composites containing two layers of stitched quadriaxial E-glass fibre fabric in an isophthalic polyester resin and the core was an end-grain balsa having a density of 175 kg/m³ and a nominal thickness of 15 mm. Material A represents a standard system in which the skins were cured directly onto the balsa core. Prior to applying the composite skins, the cores in materials B to D were first sealed using a polyester resin. Material C contained a layer of chopped strand mat (CSM) at the skin-core interface and material D a layer of fabric based on a thermoplastic polyester fibre. Further details regarding the materials and manufacturing procedures can be found in refs 4 and 5.

Test Methods

Single Cantilever Sandwich Specimen

The interfacial fracture toughness of the sandwich materials was investigated using the single cantilever sandwich (SCS) geometry test shown in Fig. 1a. Here, one end of the beam was machined away leaving a tongue approximately 50 mm long. Prior to testing, the specimens were pre-cracked by loading the specimen in a vice and applying load to the end of the beam forcing a crack to propagate along the skin-core interface. Testing was carried out at a crosshead displacement rate of 5 mm/minute. In all tests, the crack was propagated 50 mm before the specimen was unloaded. Four specimens of each type were tested. The interfacial fracture energy was calculated using a compliance calibration procedure.

A finite element analysis was undertaken in order to determine the mode-mixity at the crack tip in the SCS geometry. Here, a 9000 node mesh based on eight-noded quadratic elements was used to model the specimen. Figure 2 shows the variation of GI/GII with crack length for material A. From the figure it is apparent that the degree of mode-mixity in this specimen does not vary with crack length, remaining constant over the range of crack lengths considered.

End-Loaded Sandwich Structure

The end-loaded sandwich structure (ELSS) is shown schematically in Fig. 1b. Here, a 200 x 20 mm pre-cracked sandwich beam was fixed to a movable chariot. Testing was again carried out on at a crosshead displacement rate of 5 mm/minute and a pre-crack length of approximately 50 mm was used throughout. Load was applied through a hinge bonded to the end of the pre-cracked region and crack advance monitored using a calibrated scale painted along the interfacial region. Typically, the crack was propagated fifty millimetres before the test specimen was unloaded.

(a) Single cantilever sandwich specimen

(b) End-loaded sandwich structure

(c) Three point bend sandwich specimen

(d) Short beam shear test

Fig. 1: Schematic showing the test geometries evaluated in this programme.

Three Point Bend Sandwich Specimen

The three point bend sandwich (TPBS) specimen, Fig. 1c, is a simple flexural specimen similar in configuration to the mixed mode flexure (MMF) geometry used to characterise the interlaminar fracture toughness of high performance composites. The specimen consists of a simple beam from which the core and lower skin have been removed at one end. The specimen is then positioned on rollers (one of which is raised in order ensure than the specimen remains horizontal) and loaded at its mid-point. In this programme, specimens with dimensions 140 x 20 mm were supported on rollers positioned 120 mm apart. Once again, crack propagation is monitored optically using a calibrated scale and the fracture energy determined using a compliance calibration technique.

Fig. 2 The mode-mixity as a function of crack length for the SCS specimen geometry

Short Beam Shear Tests

A series of short beam shear tests based on the French standard NF T54-606 were undertaken on the four balsa materials in order to characterise their apparent shear strengths. In this part of the study, 50 mm wide beams were supported on cylindrical rollers positioned 200 mm apart. Load was applied by two central rollers rather than one, to avoid indentation, Fig. 1d. The crosshead displacement rate was 5 mm/min. The shear stress at rupture was determined from the expression:

$$\tau = \frac{P}{(h + h_c)B}$$

with P the maximum force, h the total sandwich thickness and h_c the core thickness, B the beam width. Six beams of each type were tested.

Climbing Drum Peel Tests

A series of climbing drum tests were conducted according to the DIN 53 295. Here, 300 x 20 mm specimens were machined leaving 25 mm tongues at each end. One end of the specimen was held in steel grip and the other end fixed to the surface of a 100 mm external diameter drum. The subsequent movement of the drum relative to the lower end of the specimen resulted in the separation of the skin and core materials. The tests were undertaken at a crosshead speed of 25 mm/min.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following sections will consider the findings of each of the five test techniques individually.

Single Cantilever Sandwich Specimen

Crack propagation in all materials was found to be stable and the resulting load-displacement traces relatively smooth. The interfacial propagation fracture energies for the four materials are shown in Fig. 3. It is clear that all of the materials exhibit similar values of fracture energy. The standard system, material A, shows an average fracture energy of approximately 900 J/m². Pretreating the balsa, material B, resulted in a small increase in the average fracture energy, however, it is probably not statistically significant. Material C containing a layer of chopped strand mat fibres at the skin-core interface exhibited an average fracture energy of approximately 800 J/m². The interface between the polyester fibre interlayer and the balsa core in material D proved to be so strong that the crack propagated up through the thermoplastic fibre interlayer and then along the composite/interlayer interface. The fracture energy associated with the interlayer-balsa interfacial region is therefore likely to be greater than the value shown in the figure.

Fig. 3 Fracture data obtained using the single cantilever sandwich geometry.

End-Loaded Sandwich Structure

The modes of crack propagation observed in the balsa specimens were similar to those observed in the SCS geometry reported above. Figure 4 contains a summary of the mean interfacial fracture energies measured on the four materials examined in this study. From the figure, it is apparent that of the four sandwich structures, material A exhibited the highest value of interfacial fracture toughness. Here, a significant amount of fibre bridging occurring between the skin and core materials was observed.

Fig. 4: Fracture data obtained using the end-loaded sandwich structure geometry.

Three Point Bend Sandwich Specimen

The load-displacement curves for the TPBS specimens were similar in appearance to those recorded during the SCS and ELSS tests with the exception that crack-propagation in material B occurred in a stick-slip mode. A subsequent optical examination of the failed sample indicated that fibre bridging was significant in materials A, C and D but limited in material B. This evidence suggests that fibre bridging has a significant influence on the stability of a propagating crack. The average fracture energies for the four balsa materials are presented in Fig. 5. From the figure it is clear that the fracture energies for materials A, C and D are similar to those determined using the SCS and ELSS geometries. Once again, material B proves to be the exception to this rule with the fracture energy being roughly fifty percent of the values measured using the other geometries. It is believed that this low value does not result from different loading conditions at the crack tip but is simply due to local variations in the quality of the skin-core interfacial region.

Short Beam Shear Tests

In all materials, initial failure occurred between the balsa blocks within the core material extending up to the skin-core interface at higher applied loads. Crack propagation in materials A, B and D occurred in an unstable manner whereas failure in system C containing a layer of chopped glass fibres was stable. The short beam shear strength data are summarised in

Fig. 6. From the figure, it is clear that the average shear strength values for these four systems are low (the interlaminar shear strength of the skins was around 30 MPa). It is also evident that the degree of scatter is quite large, probably a result of the fact that crack initiation depends on the position of joints between blocks. Material D containing the thermoplastic fibre interlayer yielded the highest value of shear strength.

The short beam shear test is often used as a quality control check in shipyards and can be employed to identify problems relating to the skin-core interface. Unfortunately, the tests on these balsa materials all yielded similar apparent shear strengths so this test is of limited use for more detailed studies of interface behaviour.

Fig. 5 : Fracture data obtained using the three point bend sandwich specimen.

Climbing Drum Peel Tests

Due to the high skin thicknesses of the balsa-based materials C and D, climbing drum peel tests were only undertaken on materials A and B. Both of these materials exhibited a stable mode of fracture in which the peel force remained roughly constant during the test. The specific moments for materials A and B were 88 and 91 Nm/m respectively. The major disadvantage of this technique is that it is only suited for the testing of relatively thin skinned systems.

Comparison of the Test Techniques

Comparing the experimental data yielded by the five test techniques enables several conclusions to be drawn. The short-beam shear test, although simple to use, is very sensitive to the quality of the balsa core and the measured shear strength depends on the position of the joints between the balsa blocks. The climbing drum peel test is a useful technique for characterising the interfacial fracture properties of sandwich materials but it is limited to the testing of thin-skinned materials. The end-loaded sandwich structure, the single cantilever sandwich and the three point bend sandwich specimen proved to be well suited to the testing of all four materials. For a given material system, different fracture energies were obtained using the specimens, Fig. 7. It is likely that the mode I/II mixity is different between the three tests and this will result in different values of G . The ELSS test involves the use of a sliding chariot and is therefore slightly more cumbersome. The SCS and TPBS geometries offer several advantages including their ease of use and the possibility of undertaking tests at very high rates of strain. Problems do arise when testing very thin-skinned sandwich structures but these can be overcome by bonding a thicker substrate to the loading arm.

Fig. 6: Fracture data from the short beam shear tests

CONCLUSIONS

Five different test geometries have been used to characterise skin-core failure in a variety of balsa-based sandwich materials. The climbing drum peel test was found to be unsuitable for tests on thick-skinned structures such as the balsa-based materials C and D. The short-beam shear test, a technique frequently used as a quality control test in shipyards, failed to

differentiate between the various balsa systems and is deemed to be unsuitable for characterising materials of this nature. The end-loaded sandwich structure, the single cantilever sandwich specimen and the three point bend sandwich specimen were well suited for testing the range of systems examined in this study.

Fig.7: Comparison of the fracture energies determined using the SCS, ELSS and the TPBS geometries

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